

CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY ON KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICES OF HAND HYGIENE, FACE MASK, AND SOCIAL DISTANCING AMONG HEALTHCARE STUDENTS DURING COVID-19 FOURTH WAVE

Fakiha Nadeem¹, Anesh Kumar², Saba Javed³, Maria Junaid⁴, Muhaba Javed⁵,
Sooraj Kumar⁶, Sham Lal^{*7}

^{1,2,3,4,5}Jinnah Sindh Medical University (SMC), Karachi

⁶Institute of Microbiology, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan,

^{*7}Associate Professor, Institute of Microbiology, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan,

^{*7}shamlal@salu.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20484537>

Keywords

2019-nCoV; Attitude; Awareness; Medical students; Pandemic; COVID-19

Article History

Received: 31 January 2026

Accepted: 16 March 2026

Published: 30 March 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Sham Lal

Abstract

Objective: To assess medical students' knowledge, attitude, and practices of hand hygiene, mask-wearing, and social distancing during the 4th wave of COVID-19 in Pakistan, and to derive insights relevant to preparedness against future infectious disease outbreaks.

Method: During the fourth wave of COVID-19 in Pakistan, 319 medical students from Jinnah Sindh Medical University (JSMU) Karachi participated in online descriptive cross-sectional research between June and August 2021 using a self-developed questionnaire. The findings were further analyzed to understand behavioral trends and preparedness measures applicable to future public health emergencies.

Results: This study involved 319 medical students, of whom 212 (66.5%) were female and 107 (33.5%) were male. Approximately 72% of participants knew enough about COVID-19. To our surprise, 53% of participants were unaware of the WHO recommended distance between two persons. Approximately half of the participants advised others to wear a mask. 88.7% urge their family members, friends, and relatives to get vaccinated. More than half (64.9%) of participants used social media platforms to raise public awareness regarding COVID-19. The findings provide valuable insight into preventive health behaviors among future healthcare professionals during a major public health crisis.

Conclusion: The study demonstrated adequate knowledge and generally positive preventive practices among medical students regarding COVID-19 safety measures. The findings also highlight the important role of medical students in community awareness and public health promotion. Although adherence to some preventive practices declined over time, the study offers useful baseline evidence for strengthening preparedness strategies, risk communication, and behavioral interventions during future infectious disease outbreaks.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Coronaviruses are positive-sense, single-strand ribonucleic acid viruses that are enveloped and non-segmented, belonging to the Corona-

viridae family. Coughing, sneezing, or inhaling respiratory droplets and fomites are the main ways that the virus spreads from person to person¹. Atypical pneumonia caused by a new

coronavirus (2019-nCoV) was initially detected and confirmed in Wuhan, China, on December 31, 2019². The first two COVID-19 cases in Pakistan were reported by the Ministry of Health on February 26, 2020³. The fourth wave of COVID-19 appeared in Pakistan in 2021, and the delta variation was becoming a new health emergency.

Acute encephalitis in the brain, dermal rashes, acute renal and hepatic damage, conjunctivitis in the skin, blood clots in the blood vessels, and loss of taste and smell are among the extrapulmonary symptoms of COVID-19, which is now regarded as a systemic illness. The best way to avoid and control this infection is still to take appropriate precautions.^{4,5} These precautions include wearing face masks, regularly washing your hands with soap or disinfecting them with hand sanitizer, maintaining a minimum social distance of two meters or six feet in busy areas, and refraining from touching your mouth, nose, or eyes with unclean hands. Healthcare workers should use N95 masks to protect themselves against the COVID-19 virus, according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Airborne particles and small droplets that the patient may have coughed up are filtered out by N95 masks.⁶

The influence of COVID-19 is magnificent, especially in developing countries like Pakistan, long-term lockdowns cannot be imposed because of economic crises.⁷ With limited resources, countries like Pakistan should adopt policies that keep medical undergraduates rationalized and well-informed about emerging public health difficulties.

According to earlier cross-sectional research conducted in Pakistan during the first three waves of COVID-19, primary healthcare professionals exhibit acceptable behavior regarding COVID-19 infection.⁸ However, as COVID-19 restrictions were relaxed, people started ignoring precautionary measures. To the best of our knowledge, no major study specifically evaluated the attitudes and knowledge of Pakistani medical students during the fourth wave of COVID-19. Individual behavior may considerably reduce morbidity and death, according to a new research.⁹ Authorities were forced to enlist medical students to help in the already

overburdened national health system after many hospitals reported a lack of medical staff; hence awareness and perception of medical students are important to combat future healthcare crises.¹⁰ Therefore, present study aimed to assess the response of medical students of JSMU toward the “new normal” including their behavior regarding social distancing and other preventive measures, as well as their role in spreading awareness among the general public during the 4th wave of COVID-19.

2. Methodology

This cross-sectional survey was conducted from June to August 2021 among medical students from several departments at Jinnah Sindh Medical University (JSMU) Karachi, including MBBS, BDS, DPT, and nursing students. The JSMU ethics review committee granted ethical permission for this study, and participant data was kept anonymous. After accounting for non-respondents at a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error, the sample size, which was calculated assuming a population size of around 4000, came out to be 319 with inflation of 10%.

Convenient non-probability sampling was used to get the data. Data was gathered using a self-administered, validated questionnaire from students who gave consent. A pilot research involving thirty students was used to validate the questionnaire. An online survey created using Google Forms was used to collect data in light of the pandemic scenario. Some of the attitude questions were scaled, but all of the KAP questions were closed-ended 1-5.

There were five sections in the questionnaire. (1) demographics which include gender, age, academic year, residence, and year of study (2) knowledge about COVID-19 (K 10), (3) Attitude (A 4), and (4) Practice (P 7). For knowledge questions, the minimum score for every individual was 8 and the maximum was 22. A score of 8-13 was considered poor knowledge, 14-18 was considered good knowledge, and 19-22 was taken as excellent knowledge. Similarly, the minimum score for attitude was 4 and the maximum was 15. The individual score of 10-15 was taken as a positive attitude. And minimum score for practice was 5 and the maximum was 19. So, an individual's

score of above 13 was taken as good practice, and below 13 was taken as poor practice.

The findings were statistically analyzed using SPSS version 22. For various factors, percentages and frequencies were calculated. To determine the relationship between mean knowledge and residency and gender, an independent t-test was used. To determine if mean knowledge and course of study were correlated, a one-way ANOVA was used. Statistical significance was defined as $P < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS:

A response rate of 92% was obtained, with 319 out of 346 undergraduate medical students completing the survey. The highest responses were received from 4th-year students (37.9%); followed by 3rd-year (25.7%), 2nd-year (17.2%), 1st-year (13.2%), and 5th-year (6.0%) students. Regarding the demographic characteristics of participants, there were 212 (66.5%) females and 107 (33.5%) males. The participants' average age was 22.6 (SD 0.773). Day scholars made up 75.9% of the total participants, while hostelites made up 24.1%. Approximately one-third of individuals had a family member with COVID-19 within the preceding six months. Participants in the research mostly learned about COVID-19 from television.

Table 1 demonstrates the knowledge of participants. The mean total knowledge score was 16 \pm 2.5 (range 8-22) with 72% of participants having good knowledge. Our

analysis suggests that the mean knowledge score of 2nd and final-year medical students was slightly higher than 1st, 3rd, and 4th-year students, but the mean knowledge score was not statistically significant with the year of study (p value=0.167). Female medical students were found to have significantly better mean knowledge scores ($M=16.585 \pm 2.29$) than male medical students ($M=15.05 \pm 2.29$) ($p=0.0001$). Day scholars were found to have a better mean ($M=16.49 \pm 0.15$) knowledge scores than hostelites ($M=15.27 \pm 0.29$) ($p=0.02$). Likewise, MBBS students had significantly better knowledge than BDS, DPT, and BSN students ($p < 0.001$). To our surprise, 53% of the participants were unaware of the WHO-recommended distance between two persons.

The majority of students had corrected knowledge about routes of transmission of coronavirus such as by respiratory droplet of an infected person (38.9%), close physical contact with an infected person (29.7%), and by touching infected surfaces (28.3%). More than half (75.2%) of participants knew about early diagnostic testing for COVID-19. The majority of participants thought that the use of a face mask, washing hands, use of alcohol-based sanitizer, and maintaining WHO-recommended social distancing will decrease the risk; while getting vaccinated will decrease the severity of infection.

Table 1. Response of study participants to COVID-19 knowledge questions

Variables	N (%)
COVID-19 transmission from person to person is	
Through respiratory droplets of an infected person	288 (38.9%)
Close physical contact with an infected person	220 (29.7%)
By eating unhygienic food	
By touching surfaces that may contain organisms (doors etc.)	23 (3.1%)
	210 (28.3%)
Recommended test for early detection/diagnosis of COVID-19 Infection	
Correct answer	
Incorrect answer	240 (75.2%)
	79 (24.8%)

The WHO recommended distance between persons is Correct answer	150 (47.0%)
Incorrect answer	169 (53.0%)
The use of a face mask decreases the risk of getting an infection Yes	312 (97.8%)
No	7 (2.2%)
Washing hands is a good measure to decrease the risk of acquiring an infection Yes	314 (98.4%)
No	5 (1.6%)
Do you believe that using an alcohol-based sanitizer is a good strategy to reduce the risk of infection? Yes	296 (92.8%)
No	23 (7.2%)
Wearing gloves lower the risk of infection Yes	291 (91.2%)
No	28 (8.8%)
Maintaining the WHO-recommended social distancing guidelines will decrease the chances of acquiring infection Yes	313 (98.1%)
No	6 (1.9%)
Do you know about the vaccine program launched by the government? Yes	302 (94.5%)
No	17 (5.3%)
Do you think getting vaccinated will decrease the severity of infection? Yes	304 (95.3%)
No	15 (4.7%)

Table 2 reports the attitudes of students. The mean attitude score was 11+/-2.2 (range 4-15). More than half of the participants (75.9%) showed a good attitude. As shown in Table 5, there was a statistically significant difference in attitude scores among genders (p=0.03). About 66.6% of participants thought that they will home isolate and would treat according to the

advice of a doctor if a member of their family is infected, whereas 16.9% thought that the infected person should be hospitalized, 5.4% believe to give self-prescribed medicine, 7.0% thought to treat an infected person with home remedies, 2.5% said that they'll be terrified and won't tell anybody outside their family and 1.6% won't do anything.

Table 2. Response of study participants to COVID-19 Attitude Questions

Question	N (%)
How do you score your risk of acquiring COVID-19 infection?	
Very low	35 (11.0%)
Low	64 (20.1%)
Neither high nor low	130 (40.8%)
High	70 (21.9%)
Very high	20 (6.3%)
What do you think will be the severity of COVID-19 if it affects you?	
Very low	
Low	33 (10.3%)
Neither high nor low	92 (28.8%)
	122 (38.2%)
High	57 (17.9%)
Very high	15 (4.7%)
What do you think the impact of precautionary measures is on reducing the risk of infection?	
Very low	10 (3.1%)
Low	15 (4.7%)
Neither high nor low	54 (16.9%)
High	142 (44.5%)
Very high	98 (30.7%)
What would you do if a member of your family is infected?	
I'll be terrified and won't tell anybody outside my family	11 (2.5%)
Hospital admission of the infected person.	75 (16.9%)
Home isolation and will treat according to the advice of a doctor.	295 (66.6%)
Start giving self-prescribed medicine.	24 (5.4%)
Start treating the infected person with home remedies.	31 (7.0%)
Do nothing.	7 (1.6%)

The mean overall practice score was 12.25 +/- 2.06 (range 5-19), as seen in Table 3. 79.6% of participants took effective protection against COVID-19. Female medical students were found to have a significantly better practice of preventive measures than male medical students (p=0.03). There was no significant

difference in COVID-19 practice scores among different age groups, their residence, year of study, and course of study. [Table 4] To our surprise, only 15.4% of participants never share their personal articles with their friends and colleagues. About 77.1% of participants were vaccinated.

Table 3. Response of study participants towards COVID-19 practice questions

Questions	N (%)
Do you wear a mask when you leave your house?	
Yes	305 (95.6%)
No	14 (4.4%)

<p>Do you properly dispose of used masks and tissue after usage?</p> <p>Every time Often Sometimes Rarely Never</p>	<p>177 (55.5%) 84 (26.3%) 47 (14.7%) 6 (1.9%) 5 (1.6%)</p>
<p>Do you share your articles (Water bottles, pens, towels, comb, etc.) with your friends or colleague?</p> <p>Every time Often Sometimes Rarely Never</p>	<p>36 (11.3%) 70 (21.9%) 101 (31.7%) 63 (19.7%) 49 (15.4%)</p>
<p>Do you avoid going out in crowded places or family gatherings?</p> <p>Every time Often</p>	<p>42 (13.2%) 111 (34.8%)</p>
<p>Sometimes Rarely Never</p>	<p>103 (32.3%) 49 (15.4%) 14 (4.4%)</p>
<p>Do you maintain the required distance to decrease infection risk outside the home?</p> <p>Yes No</p>	<p>205 (64.3%) 114 (35.7%)</p>
<p>How much time do you take while washing your hands?</p> <p>5secs 10secs 15secs 20secs</p>	<p>49 (15.4%) 126 (39.5%) 73 (22.9%) 71 (22.3%)</p>
<p>Have you received your COVID-19 vaccine?</p> <p>Yes No</p>	<p>246 (77.1%) 73 (22.9%)</p>

Table 4. Comparisons of knowledge, attitude and practice score among demographic variables.

Variables	Subgroups	Knowledge	Attitude	Practice
Age (Years)	18-19 year	17.29 +/- 2.49	10.62 +/- 2.21	12.33 +/- 1.89
	20-21 year	16.85 +/- 2.67	11.0 +/- 2.22	12.16 +/- 2.23
	22-23 year	16.86 +/- 2.47	11.36 +/- 1.97	12.37 +/- 1.96
	24-25 year	17.92 +/- 2.17	2.59 +/- 0.72	12.07 +/- 1.80
	P-value	0.37	0.11	0.8
Gender	Male	15.43 +/- 2.73	10.53 +/- 2.24	10.53 +/- 2.24
	Female	16.58 +/- 2.29	11.29 +/- 2.08	11.29 +/- 2.08
	P-value	0.0001	0.003	0.03
Resident	Home	16.49 +/- 0.15	11.17 +/- 2.14	12.15 +/- 2.03

	Hostel P-value	15.27 +/- 0.29 0.02	10.62 +/- 2.18 0.05	12.58 +/- 2.14 0.11
Year of Study	First-year	17.16 +/- 2.53	10.57 +/- 2.18	12.64 +/- 1.97
	Second-year	17.50 +/- 2.70	10.83 +/- 2.27	11.84 +/- 2.25
	Third-year	16.54 +/- 2.74	11 +/- 2.24	12.35 +/- 2.24
	Fourth-year	16.84 +/- 2.44	11.39 +/- 2.02	12.23 +/- 1.91
	Final Year	17.63 +/- 1.77	10.57 +/- 2.11	12.31 +/- 1.76
	P-value	0.16	0.15	0.41

Approximately half of the participants mostly advise someone who is not wearing a mask to put one on, while nearly half of them usually advised people to keep their social distance while they are out in public. Most of the participants (88.7%) urge their family members, friends, and relatives to get vaccinated, and 90.9% of participants gave their family members proper guidance about COVID-19. More than half (64.9%) of participants use social media platforms to raise

public awareness regarding COVID-19 [Table 5]

The correlation analysis between the total knowledge score and total attitude score yielded a strong positive correlation ($p < 0.001$) between them. While the correlation between knowledge and practice showed a weak negative correlation between them ($p = 0.73$). The correlation analysis between practice and attitude yielded no significant correlation between these two variables.

Table 5. Response of study participants towards COVID-19 awareness questions

Variables	N (%)
Do you advise someone who isn't wearing a mask in public to put one on?	
Every time	
Often	72 (22.6%)
Sometimes	83 (26.0%)
Rarely	81 (25.4%)
Never	49 (15.4%)
	34 (10.7%)
Do you advise people to keep their social distance while they're out in public?	
Every time	
Often	53 (16.6%)
Sometimes	74 (23.2%)
Rarely	83 (26.0%)
Never	63 (19.7%)
	46 (14.4%)
Did you urge your family members, friends and relatives to get vaccinated?	
Yes	
No	283 (88.7%)
	36 (11.3%)
Have you given your family members proper guidance/awareness about COVID-19?	
Yes	
No	290 (90.9%)
	29 (9.1%)

<p>Do you use social media platforms to raise public awareness regarding COVID-19?</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>	<p>207 (64.9%)</p> <p>112 5.1%</p>
--	------------------------------------

4. DISCUSSION

Since the beginning of the epidemic, the WHO has advised taking precautions to stop the spread of COVID-19. One of the most frequent causes of bad adoption would be a lack of awareness about sickness. Prior research examined medical students' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors just after the epidemic was declared.¹¹ Given that the pandemic has been going on for more than 1.5 years, the fourth wave of COVID-19 may exhibit different attitudes and behaviors.

This study found that 72% of participants had good knowledge, which is in line with an Indian research that revealed that 86.7% of respondents had accurate understanding.¹² According to this study, medical students in their second and final years had somewhat higher mean knowledge scores than those in their first, third, and fourth years; nevertheless, this difference was not statistically significant (P Value=0.167); which is contrary with the study conducted in Uganda in which knowledge was significantly associated with 4th year (p value=0.001).¹³ MBBS students have significantly better knowledge than BDS, DPT, and Nursing students (p value= 0.001, which is somehow consistent with another study in which MBBS students had better knowledge than dental and other allied health students. But the same study reports better knowledge among nursing students which is contrary to our findings.¹⁴ This discrepancy could be due to the fact that most of the respondents were from MBBS.

Our analysis showed that female medical students have significantly better mean knowledge scores (16.585 +/- 22.29) than male medical students (16.58 +/- 2.29), with a p-value of 0.0001. Similarly, female medical students were more likely to have a positive attitude (p value=0.003) which is consistent with another study conducted in Pakistan.¹⁵

The majority of respondents (75%) had a good attitude and agreed that they would separate themselves at home if any of their family

members contracted the infection, as information is a prerequisite to attitude and eventually behavioral change. This is in line with research done in Afghanistan, a neighboring nation.¹⁶ Because attitude influences behavioral actions, we found that 95% of the population wear a mask, 64% of them maintain the WHO recommended distance at public places, 39.5% wash their hands for 10 seconds, 22.9% for 15 sec, and 22.3% for 20 seconds. And 34.8% often avoid attending family gatherings or crowded places, 32.3% sometimes avoid, and only 4% of respondents attend family gatherings. We also found out that 77.1% of the students were vaccinated in the 4th wave of COVID-19 in Pakistan. The college authorities should encourage all medical students to be vaccinated against COVID-19.

These findings suggest that most participants followed appropriate preventive measures. In contrast to previous study on Indonesian medical students, where the association between knowledge was minimal, the correlation analysis between the overall knowledge score and the total attitude score produced a substantial positive correlation (p<0.001).¹⁷ We also found out a correlation between knowledge and practice which showed a weak negative correlation (p=0.73), and from this negative correlation, it is evident that with the passage of time practice among medical students is declining despite good knowledge. This is a dilemma because if the future healthcare professionals of the country start ignoring the practice of preventive measures, then the common people won't practice them too. The majority of participants in our study were aware of the proper techniques for early diagnosis and detection of COVID-19 infection, and they believed that wearing face masks, washing their hands, using alcohol-based sanitizer, and adhering to WHO-recommended social distancing would reduce the risk, while receiving a vaccination would lessen the severity of infection. Therefore,

medical students were generally well-versed in the required level of knowledge, which is comparable to a prior study done in Pakistan where 71.7% had sufficient knowledge.¹⁵

The majority of students correctly selected fever (22.5%), dry cough (17.5%), SOB (22.10%), and sore throat (12%) as the primary COVID-19 symptoms. Hence overall they had adequate knowledge about signs and symptoms. Similar findings were reported in a northwest Ethiopia study.¹⁸ In contrast to our findings, another study from Pakistan reported low knowledge among the general population including students¹⁹ and a study conducted on the locals of Karachi reported suboptimal knowledge.²⁰ Surprisingly, 53% of respondents were unaware of the WHO-recommended safe distance, and the most probable reason for not knowing the exact distance is using broadcast media. i.e., television and social media platforms were the main sources of information while fewer participants relied on the official government website (covid.gov.pk). It was observed that 54.20% of participants obtained information from television, while Facebook was the second most common source at 20.20%. Another research conducted in Pakistan revealed similar results: 81.5% of participants sought information on COVID-19 from television, 46.65% from social media, and 45.6% from newspapers and other sources.¹⁵ However, another survey from Pakistan found that social media (39%) and television (29%) were the primary sources of information.¹¹ Our data suggest that there is a need to improve the reliable resources of information and platforms. Resources that provide incorrect information should be censored so that people can get the right information and implement it accordingly.

This study has several limitations. Due to limited cooperation from BDS, DPT, and nursing students, the collection of more diverse and representative data was constrained. Despite these limitations, the findings provide useful insight into students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices during the study period. These results may assist policymakers in strengthening information dissemination systems and ensuring that accurate and reliable health information is made accessible to meet current and future public health needs.

5. CONCLUSION:

The findings of this study demonstrate that medical students possessed a good level of knowledge regarding the symptoms, transmission, and preventive measures of COVID-19 during the fourth wave of the pandemic in Pakistan. The participants also showed a positive attitude and generally appropriate preventive practices. However, a gradual decline in adherence to preventive measures across successive waves was observed, which is concerning as medical students represent future healthcare professionals. Therefore, strengthening public health communication remains essential, and accurate updated information should continue to be disseminated through social media, print and electronic platforms. In addition, medical students should consistently follow recommended preventive measures and actively contribute to public awareness campaigns. Overall the study provides useful baseline evidence for improving preparedness strategies, risk communication, and behavioral interventions for future infectious disease outbreaks and public health emergencies.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge Dr. Aliya Jafri for her assistance in obtaining Ethical Review Committee (ERC) approval from the Ethical Review Board of Jinnah Sindh Medical University.

Disclaimer

None

Conflicts of interest

None

Funding Disclosure

None

6. REFERENCES:

Weiss SR Leibowitz JL. Coronavirus pathogenesis. *Adv Virus Res* [Internet]. 2011;81:85-164. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-385885-6.00009-2>

- Lau H, Khosrawipour V, Kocbach P, Mikolajczyk A, Schubert J, Bania J, et al. The positive impact of lockdown in Wuhan on containing the COVID-19 outbreak in China. *J Travel Med* [Internet]. 2020;27(3). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jtm/taaa037>
- Waris A, Atta UK, Ali M, Asmat A, Baset A. COVID-19 outbreak: current scenario of Pakistan. *New Microbes New Infect.* 2020;35:100681. doi: 10.1016/j.nmni.2020.100681.
- Thakur V, Ratho RK, Kumar P, Bhatia SK, Bora I, Mohi GK, Saxena SK, Devi M, Yadav D, Mehariya S. Multi-Organ Involvement in COVID-19: Beyond Pulmonary Manifestations. *J Clin Med.* 2021;10:446. doi: 10.3390/jcm10030446.
- Mumtaz S, Gul S. Third wave of COVID-19 Epidemic in Pakistan. *Life and Science.* 2021;2:1. doi: 10.37185/LnS.1.1.198.
- Cash R, Patel V. Has COVID-19 subverted global health? *The Lancet.* 2020;395:1687-1688. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31089-8.
- Ahmad T, Haroon H, Baig M, Hui J. Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Pandemic and Economic Impact. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2020;36. doi: 10.12669/pjms.36.COVID19-S4.2638.
- Hussain I, Majeed A, Imran I, Ullah M, Hashmi FK, Saeed H, Chaudhry MO, Rasool MF. Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices Toward COVID-19 in Primary Healthcare Providers: A Cross-Sectional Study from Three Tertiary Care Hospitals of Peshawar, Pakistan. *J Community Health.* 2021;46:441-449. doi: 10.1007/s10900-020-00879-9.
- Anderson RM, Heesterbeek H, Klinkenberg D, Hollingsworth TD. How will country-based mitigation measures influence the course of the COVID-19 epidemic? *The Lancet.* 2020;395:931-934. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30567-5.
- Miller DG, Pierson L, Doernberg S. The Role of Medical Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Ann Intern Med.* 2020;173:145-146. doi: 10.7326/M20-1281.
- Ali S, Alam BF, Farooqi F, Almas K, Noreen S. Dental and Medical Students' Knowledge and Attitude toward COVID-19: A Cross-Sectional Study from Pakistan. *Eur J Dent.* 2020;14:S97-S104. doi: 10.1055/s-0040-1719219.
- Maheshwari S, Gupta P, Sinha R, Rawat P. Knowledge, attitude, and practice towards coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) among medical students: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Acute Disease.* 2020;9:100. doi: 10.4103/2221-6189.283886.
- Olum R, Kajjimu J, Kanyike AM, Chekwech G, Wekha G, Nassozi DR, Kemigisa J, Mulyamboga P, Muhoozi OK, Nsenga L, et al. Perspective of Medical Students on the COVID-19 Pandemic: Survey of Nine Medical Schools in Uganda. *JMIR Public Health Surveill.* 2020;6:e19847. doi: 10.2196/19847.
- Ikhaq A, Bint E Riaz H, Bashir I, Ijaz F. Awareness and Attitude of Undergraduate Medical Students towards 2019-novel Corona virus. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2020;36. doi: 10.12669/pjms.36.COVID19-S4.2636.
- Noreen K, Rubab Z, Umar M, Rehman R, Baig M, Baig F. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices against the growing threat of COVID-19 among medical students of Pakistan. *PLoS One.* 2020;15:e0243696. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0243696.
- Nemat A, Raufi N, Sediqi MF, Rasib AR, Asady A. Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of Medical Students Regarding COVID-19 in Afghanistan: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Risk Manag Healthc Policy.* 2021;Volume 14:1491-1497. doi: 10.2147/RMHP.S308039.

Adli I, Widyahening IS, Lazarus G, Phowira J, Baihaqi LA, Ariffandi B, Putera AM, Nugraha D, Gamalliel N, Findyartini A. Knowledge, attitude, and practice related to the COVID-19 pandemic among undergraduate medical students in Indonesia: A nationwide cross-sectional study. *PLoS One*. 2022;17:e0262827. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0262827.

Taddese AA, Azene ZN, Merid MW, Muluneh AG, Geberu DM, Kassa GM, Yenit MK, Tilahun SY, Gelaye KA, Mekonnen HS, et al. Knowledge and attitude of the communities towards COVID-19 and associated factors among Gondar City residents, northwest Ethiopia: A community based cross-sectional study. *PLoS One*. 2021;16:e0248821. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0248821.

Tariq S, Tariq S, Baig M, Saeed M. Knowledge, Awareness, and Practices Regarding the Novel Coronavirus Among a Sample of a Pakistani Population: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Disaster Med Public Health Prep*. 2022;16:934-939. doi: 10.1017/dmp.2020.408.

Mubeen S, Kamal S, Kamal S, Balkhi F. Knowledge and awareness regarding spread and prevention of COVID-19 among the young adults of Karachi. *J Pak Med Assoc*. 2020;1. doi: 10.5455/JPMA.40.

